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Soviet Invasion of Czechoslovakia: Combating a Political Infection in a Friendly State

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Abstract: *The purpose of this paper is to explain why the Soviet government opted for invasion rather than for possible other strategies during the Prague Spring? What were the justifications for a military invasion? Secondly, what were the consequences of the military approach? What did Soviet leadership achieve and lose as a result of their handling of the Czechoslovak crisis? To answer those questions, the first part of the paper will provide the basic explanation of Soviet decision-making process, the difficulties on intelligence collecting, the perspective of Eastern Europe on reforms in Czechoslovakia, and other factors that influenced the emergence of the crisis. The second part will cover the pre and post-invasion Czechoslovakia affairs, and crisis consequences to Europe-USSR and US-USSR relations.*

Keywords: *Prague Spring; USSR; Czechoslovakia; Cold-War;*

Introduction

In January of 1968, Czechoslovakia's government leader Alexander Dubcek initiated a democratization program consisting of unprecedented economic and political liberalization to revitalize the nation after decades of harsh and oppressive Communist regime.¹ Dubcek's reforms were intended to end censorship of the media and to grant citizens more freedom of speech. As a result, the reforms led to an explosion of artistic expression, free discussion, and alignment with democratic ideals.² However, Dubcek's government did not intend to challenge the Soviet national security interests and it kept acknowledging the full legitimacy of the Czechoslovak Communist

¹Anna J. Stoneman, "Socialism with a Human Face: the Leadership and Legacy of the Prague Spring," *The History Teacher* 49, (2015): 103. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24810503>.

²Anna J. Stoneman, "Socialism with a Human Face: the Leadership and Legacy of the Prague Spring," 103.

Party. Nevertheless, the Soviet government saw a potential threat in the Czechoslovak reforms.³ As a result, the democratization process was curbed by the Soviet-led invasion in August 1968, while the Prague Spring became the trigger for a reemergence of social activism and democratization that significantly contributed to the collapse of Communist regime later on.

This paper will focus on the fact that the military approach seemed to be the last resort option and was not expected at all. The purpose of this paper is to explain why the Soviet government opted for invasion rather than for possible other strategies? What were the justifications for a military invasion? Secondly, what were the consequences of the military approach? What did Soviet leadership achieve and lose as a result of their handling of the Czechoslovak crisis?

To answer those questions, the first part of the paper will provide the basic explanation of Soviet decision-making process, the difficulties on intelligence collecting, the perspective of Eastern Europe on reforms in Czechoslovakia, and other factors that influenced the emergence of the crisis. The second part will cover the pre and post-invasion Czechoslovakia affairs, and crisis consequences to Europe-USSR and US-USSR relations.

1. Why did Soviet government opt for invasion rather than for a possible other strategy?

a) USSR decision-making process

No single actor was responsible for the Soviet foreign policy.⁴ Instead, there was a process of political interaction among the top leadership in the Politburo and the important bureaucratic figures from Central Committee level. There was no influence of pure institutional and organizational interest in Soviet foreign policy actions. Instead, bureaucratic politics was constructed upon a division of labour and responsibilities among Politburo members in different policy areas.⁵ As a result, main state branches participating in decision-making included the Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union (CPSU), the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Soviet Committee for State Security (KGB), and the Ministry of Defense.⁶

³ Jiri Valenta, "The Bureaucratic Politics Paradigm and the Soviet Invasion of Czechoslovakia," *Political Science Quarterly* 94, (1979): 59. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2150156>.

⁴ Jiri Valenta, "The Bureaucratic Politics Paradigm and the Soviet Invasion of Czechoslovakia," 57.

⁵ Ibid, 57.

⁶ Ibid.

Additionally, departments dealing with domestic affairs and regional party politics outside of Russian national republics also had a right to participate in decision making.

According to Tatu's observation of Soviet politics in the 1960s, coalitions among Soviet government were loose, temporary, issue-oriented and there were heterogeneous alliances of convenience among various powerful subgroups that capable to pursue own policies.⁷ Riker adds that uniting in a single alliance is not necessarily motivated by ideological concerns, rather by calculations of potential payoffs, compatibility and estimation of conflicts of interests.⁸

As a result, Soviet doctrines at the time of crisis in Czechoslovakia was no more than inconsistent rationalizations of actions implemented in the pressure of domestic and international struggle.⁹ Moreover, the collective leadership in Moscow could not be seen as a force which under any circumstances strove to preserve the conservatism and caution in Soviet policies, thus could not deliver the stability to the world.

Particularly, in the case of the Prague Spring, such Soviet leadership was the source of instability that generated objectively inexplicable choices.¹⁰ At the Kremlin, each player, participating in a decision-making process, depending on their bureaucratic position and interests in internal politics, had a different interpretation of Dubcek's reforms. Consequently, decision-makers ended up with contrary versions of probable further developments and disagreed on the measures needed to stabilize the crisis.¹¹

Supporters of intervention among Soviet leadership saw it as a zero-sum game where Czechoslovaks would lose in case of USSR's triumph.¹² They aimed to remove Dubcek by force, as a result, to 'cure' the 'disease' in the allied state. Meanwhile, they hoped to obtain leverage on dissidents and reformers within domestic politics. By contrast, non-supporters of military intervention saw the crisis as a non-zero-sum game, hence were keen to resolve the crisis by economic and diplomatic means.¹³ Some of them looked forward to supporting Dubcek's regime

⁷ Ibid, 64.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹Anatole Shub, "Lessons of Czechoslovakia," *Foreign Affairs* 47, (1969): 268.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/20039372>.

¹⁰ Anatole Shub, "Lessons of Czechoslovakia," 268.

¹¹ Jiri Valenta, "The Bureaucratic Politics Paradigm and the Soviet Invasion of Czechoslovakia," 60.

¹² Ibid, 65.

¹³ Ibid.

and protect it from two extremes – anti-Soviet movements and discredited supporters of Novotny.¹⁴

Dawisha suggests a different version of explanation to the Soviet's decision to invade Prague in 1968. She claims that, in times of crises, leaders, under the stress, tend to play down the differences, retreat to safe, and adopt a black and white dichotomy of the world.¹⁵ Thus, high tension of the crisis obscured the Soviet leaders' perception of reality. However, she still admits the significant influence of internal infighting amongst Soviet leadership on the decision to invade Czechoslovakia. Thus, she concludes that Brezhnev's decision to invade was significantly influenced by discontents in the Central Committee and his rivals in Politburo.¹⁶

As a result, USSR leadership had several choices on Czechoslovakia's further fate: 1) Soviets could allow reforms in Prague to evolve and to observe, hoping for the best outcome for the USSR; 2) Soviets could negotiate, with pressure or persuasion implemented if necessary, to protect their interests; 3) use of power to impose control.¹⁷ Eventually, Soviets preferred the last option.

Soviets observed the developments in Czechoslovakia for the first three months. Later on, on March 23, 1968, Dubcek and Soviet leadership arranged an official meeting in Dresden where the former refused Soviet's demands to curb the reforms.¹⁸ Soviets attempted to put pressure on Dubcek, which did not encourage him to obey. Furthermore, USSR leadership tried to exert psychological pressure by carrying out military training around and within the Czechoslovak borders.¹⁹ Finally, after the meeting between Warsaw Alliance members on July 14, 1968, in Warsaw, Soviets claimed to authorize the use of force and invade Czechoslovakia.²⁰ As a result of negotiation between Warsaw Pact members, Bratislava Declaration was ratified according to which Soviets obtained a right to intervene only if a multi-party system will be introduced to

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ Kieran Williams, "New Sources on Soviet Decision Making during the 1968 Czechoslovak Crisis," *Europe Asia Studies* 48, no. 3 (1996): 460. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/152736>.

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ John C. Campbell, "Czechoslovakia: American Choices, Past and Future," *Canadian Slavonic Papers* 11, (1969): 13, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40866200>.

¹⁸ Ibid, 106.

¹⁹ Jiri Valenta, "Revolutionary Change, Soviet Intervention, and "Normalization" in East-Central Europe," *Comparative Politics* 16, (1984): 136. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/421602>.

²⁰ Anna J. Stoneman, "Socialism with a Human Face: the Leadership and Legacy of the Prague Spring," 106.

challenge the Czechoslovak Communist Party while still emphasizing Czechoslovakia's legitimacy for the sovereignty and independence.²¹

However, according to Bromke, the more tolerant position would allow Soviets not only protect their basic interests but even have transformed the situation to their advantage.²² He adds that Czechoslovak reforms did not, in fact, threaten the USSR because firstly, top leadership, including Dubcek himself, were communist who rejected pre-1948 multi-party system.²³ Had they more time, they would probably curb democracy in the state further. Secondly, Dubcek did not want to abandon Warsaw Pact because he was convinced that Soviet-Czechoslovak alliance will serve the interest of the latter. However, leadership at Kremlin politically improvised at last minute and decided to invade Czechoslovakia knowing that it will lead to unintended international consequences.²⁴

USSR leader Brezhnev was initially against any change of leadership in Czechoslovakia. However, witnessing the Novotny's way of ruling, mainly dictatorial control of the state affairs that led to growing resentment amongst the local communist population, failed policies, and absence of coherence amongst his closest associates, Brezhnev found Dubcek's new programs more attractive.²⁵ Declaring that his visit was not aimed to solve Czechoslovak problems, Brezhnev made clear that Soviet leadership does not take sides between Czechoslovak communist leaders. However, Brezhnev did emphasize the importance of Warsaw Pact unity in defending the interests of the socialist block from the potential US-led aggression.²⁶ As a result, due to the indifference of Soviet leadership to the Novotny, the latter lost legitimacy and lost his access to state military resources. Novotny had to resign from his position as First Secretary.²⁷

According to "Resolution of the Communist Party of Czechoslovakia's Central Committee Plenum", Alexander Dubcek replaced Novotny as a new leader of CCP on January 1958.²⁸ The

²¹ Ibid, 106.

²² Adam Bromke, "Czechoslovakia and the World," *Canadian Slavonic Papers* 10, (1968): 583, www.jstor.org/stable/40866193.

²³ Bromke, "Czechoslovakia and the World," 583.

²⁴ Ibid, 583.

²⁵ Jeremi Suri, "The Promise and Failure of 'Developed Socialism': The Soviet 'Thaw' and Crucible of the Prague Spring," *Contemporary European History* 15, (2006): 144. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20081303>.

²⁶ Ibid, 144.

²⁷ Ibid, 145.

²⁸ Ibid.

newly appointed leader immediately started to implement 'Action Program' to improve conditions among society. He endorsed an open exchange of views on the local government functioning. Meanwhile, witnessing Hungary's failed attempt to withdraw from the Warsaw Pact, Dubcek stressed the leading role of the Party and admitted the importance of acknowledging the Soviet influence in Eastern Europe.²⁹ Had Dubcek's reforms succeeded, Brezhnev would have followed the Czechoslovak example and encourage Soviet leadership to issue dynamic reforms to revitalize weakened domestic institutions while still preserving strong control as a part of his 'developed socialism' program that centred around mass mobilization.³⁰

Both leaders looked forward to strengthening the Communist Party's authority, however, they could not agree on tactics. Williams claims that Dubcek's regime, welcoming openly the criticism from students as well as from intellectuals, looked shaky, whereas Dubcek himself appeared to be uncertain and often filled with hesitation regarding political decisions.³¹ Soviet leadership was also concerned about the freedom the society gained to express their negative sentiments, especially the active involvement of youth, towards the Dubcek's government and its consequences. Soviets wanted to maintain the social stability in the state while Dubcek's intended radicalism was more orthodox within the framework of socialist ideology.³²

Attempts to reform socialism in Czechoslovakia transformed into open protests against the Soviet leadership thus made Brezhnev to panic because he lost control over the events in Czechoslovakia and witnessed his worst fears. On July 4, the Soviets sent a letter to Dubcek's government claiming that recent reforms would weaken the influence of the Communist Party and thus the position of socialism in Czechoslovakia.³³ According to Brezhnev, a reconsolidation of the power of the Czechoslovak Communist Party (CPCz) would be a way out from the crisis. A strong Party would control the media and flow of the news across the state. For instance, according to "Letter from L. Brezhnev to A. Dubcek proposing Another Bilateral Meeting" written in 1968, CPCz would limit the 'right-wing', 'burgeons-liberal' voices in the media.³⁴ Moreover, CPCz would easily spread its

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Ibid, 148.

³¹ Ibid.

³² Ibid.

³³ Jeremi Suri, "The Promise and Failure of 'Developed Socialism': The Soviet 'Thaw' and Crucible of the Prague Spring," 151.

³⁴ Timothy A. Sayle, "Andropov's Hungarian Complex," *Cold War History* 9, no. 3, (2009): 431.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14682740902764528>.

communist ideology across the revolting citizens and convey the message that any shift from socialism was not in their interest.³⁵ Additionally, Brezhnev condemned the supporters of political pluralism as a substitution to the Communist Party's monopoly of power. The Soviet government called on Dubcek to take actions against the anti-socialist movements, to normalize domestic affairs, and to mobilize all communists.³⁶

Although Brezhnev did not want to issue an invasion and send tanks into Czechoslovak capital, recent regional developments in Prague as well as in other regional USSR satellite states left him little of choice.³⁷ However, because for the time of Prague Spring, Brezhnev had already strong position in Kremlin through outmanoeuvring other contenders, he was not pressured into the issuing an invasion by Politburo. Thus, while Brezhnev supported the idea of establishing 'developed socialism' through the implementation of Dubcek's reforms, he could not tolerate the revolts against the USSR's regional hegemony though.³⁸

Eventually, Soviets realized that they could afford neither a split of Czechoslovakia nor an occupation of the state.³⁹ Hence, Soviets' invasion plan was quite accurate to ensure normal functioning of the state. Warsaw Pact troops were ordered: 1) not to disarm Czechoslovak Army units and to leave the areas where latter operate; 2) to leave small localities while in cities to control parks and other open areas; 3) not to block the buildings belonging to Party organs; 4) ensure normal functioning of local banks.⁴⁰

The Committee for State Security (KGB), under the leadership of Yuri Andropov, contributed significantly to the preparation and course of the occupation of Czechoslovakia. According to an agreement between Soviet State Security Apparatus and Ministry of Interior of Czechoslovakia, KGB officers and representatives would be involved in the supervision, intelligence collection and

³⁵ Timothy A. Sayle, "Andropov's Hungarian Complex," 431.

³⁶ Jeremi Suri, "The Promise and Failure of 'Developed Socialism': The Soviet 'Thaw' and Crucible of the Prague Spring," 151.

³⁷ Kieran Williams, "New Sources on Soviet Decision Making during the 1968 Czechoslovak Crisis," 459.

³⁸ Ibid, 459.

³⁹ Fred H. Eidlin, "Capitulation, Resistance and the Framework of Normalization: the August 1968 Invasion of Czechoslovakia and the Czechoslovak Response," *Journal of Peace Research* 18, (1981): 327.

<http://www.jstor.org/stable/423536>.

⁴⁰ Fred H. Eidlin, "Capitulation, Resistance and the Framework of Normalization: the August 1968 Invasion of Czechoslovakia and the Czechoslovak Response," 321.

dealing with counter-intelligence activities within the Czechoslovak state.⁴¹ As a result, on 4 June 1968, one of the KGB active officers in Czechoslovakia before Soviet invasion was Mikhail Sagatelyan, operating undercover as a foreign correspondent of Communist Party journal - *Izvestia* reported to the supreme leader of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union (CPSU) that he had contacted some leaders amongst Czechoslovak government, namely Chnoupek. Chnoupek was a member of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Czechoslovakia (CPC).⁴² Sagatelyan recommended CPC leadership to establish a group that would cooperate with the Soviet government and as a consequence would remove Alexander Dubcek. As a result, the KGB office in Prague was busy identifying and communicating with Czechoslovakia Communist Party members as well as amongst local police forces who found themselves sympathetic to a Soviet government.⁴³

In deciding on Czechoslovakia's fate, leadership at Moscow first and foremost was concerned with the preservation of Communist ideology in its satellite state. Eastern European Soviet allies constituted the significant part of the Kremlin-led 'world socialist system' idea.⁴⁴ However, Dubcek's reforms represented serious damage to the cause of world socialism. Unsurprisingly, on 14 and 15 July 1968, during the meeting in Warsaw between the leadership of Poland, East Germany, Bulgaria, and Hungary, Brezhnev fiercely criticized crisis in Prague claiming that Dubcek's reforms snowballed out of control and Czechoslovakia is almost on the path of open rejection of socialism principles.⁴⁵ Brezhnev formulated the 'domino theory' referring to Prague Spring as a challenge to the Communist Party that would lead to the demise of Communism in Czechoslovakia as well as would negatively influence 'the entire socialist system', and 'the whole world communist movement' around the world.⁴⁶ Thus, Soviet leadership demonstrated that it would not ignore the deviance of Warsaw Alliance members from the common Eastern bloc discipline.⁴⁷ In addition, increasing Sino-Soviet disputes motivated the government at the Kremlin

⁴¹ Pavel Žáček, "The KGB and the Czechoslovak State Security Apparatus in August 1968," *The Journal of Slavic Military Studies* 2, no. 4, (2016): 627. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13518046.2016.1232561>.

⁴² Pavel Žáček, "The KGB and the Czechoslovak State Security Apparatus in August 1968," 627.

⁴³ *Ibid*, 628.

⁴⁴ Peter Summerscale, "Is Eastern Europe a Liability to the Soviet Union?" *International Affairs* 57, (1981): 586. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2619861>.

⁴⁵ Jeremi Suri, "The Promise and Failure of 'Developed Socialism': The Soviet 'Thaw' and Crucible of the Prague Spring," 152.

⁴⁶ *Ibid*, 152.

⁴⁷ *Ibid*.

to maintain ideological orthodoxy amongst Eastern European satellite states, to remain loyal to a Soviet version of Socialism and to isolate China in the world communist movement.⁴⁸

Moreover, leadership at Kremlin saw Dubcek's government as ungrateful for all that the USSR had done since World War II and liberation of the state in 1945.⁴⁹ Soviets believed that Czechoslovaks must follow the correct political behaviour. Soviets expected certain etiquette of reliability, transparency and loyalty and any deviations from those standards perceived by the former as a state of political caution.⁵⁰ Brezhnev's speech during the meetings between Soviet and Czechoslovak government representatives clearly demonstrated that where he claimed that 'between political leaders without trust there is no love'.⁵¹

At the same time, from the Soviets' perspective, there was a risk that Dubcek's government might not be able to control the initiated developments for very long.⁵² Soviets were afraid that the Czechoslovak leader did not have full control over the domestic situation.⁵³ The split among the leadership between reformist and those who opposed them was the sign of coming uncertainty. As a result, according to Soviets, local Communist Party might have lost control sometime after, while the alliance with Kremlin might have loosened and as a result, might have weakened entire Soviet position and authority in the region.⁵⁴

b) Intelligence collection by the Soviets

Incomplete and distorted information received by Soviets could have significantly escalated the decision-making favoring the invasion. During the Novotny's leadership, Soviets established a secure communication system to obtain more or less accurate information.⁵⁵ However, as Dubcek came to power, Soviets had lost control over that system and mostly lacked adequate intelligence. As a result, East German, Polish and Czechoslovak anti-reformists had to assist in the provision of information to the Soviets.⁵⁶

⁴⁸ Peter Summerscale, "Is Eastern Europe a Liability to the Soviet Union?" 586.

⁴⁹ Kieran Williams, "New Sources on Soviet Decision Making during the 1968 Czechoslovak Crisis," 460.

⁵⁰ Ibid, 461.

⁵¹ Ibid.

⁵² John C. Campbell. "Czechoslovakia: American Choices, Past and Future," 21.

⁵³ Jiri Valenta, "Revolutionary Change, Soviet Intervention, and "Normalization" in East-Central Europe," 136.

⁵⁴ Ibid, 136.

⁵⁵ Jiri Valenta, "The Bureaucratic Politics Paradigm and the Soviet Invasion of Czechoslovakia," 68.

⁵⁶ Ibid, 68.

The KGB was another major intelligence supplier for the Soviets. The organization was heavily influenced by Soviet representatives who had been adversely affected by Dubcek's reformism and supported the invasion of Czechoslovakia.⁵⁷ On the distorted reports generated by these groups, Dubcek and his supporters were portrayed as an inferior force among the Czechoslovak political elite who relied majorly on the support of radical pressure groups and who were potential agents of the Western powers. In reality, however, Dubcek and his allies were a small group fearing a loss of power, at the same time they were representatives of popular opposition among the party members.⁵⁸

c) Warsaw Pact members' and Czechoslovakia anti-reformists' influence on invasion

Soviets were concerned about the spillover effect that other Warsaw Pact members would be 'negatively' influenced by democratization in Czechoslovakia.⁵⁹ Moreover, East German leader Ulbricht and Polish leader Gomulka also saw a threat in Dubcek's reforms to their own internal affairs and perceived the Soviet intervention as a chance to improve their positions at home as well as in Soviet bloc in general.⁶⁰ For instance, in Poland, students organized demonstrations demanding the reforms issued similar in Czechoslovakia.⁶¹ The case curbed the relations between Gomulka and Dubcek even further. The Soviet Union, in turn, was also internally influenced by those reforms and at least some part of local intellectuals adopted those ideas.⁶²

Soviets were allegedly invited to restore the order by some individuals amongst Czechoslovak government.⁶³ Within inner politics, some collaborators actively opposed the reforms and were sympathetic to Soviet interference.⁶⁴ For instance, Presidium members such as Comrade Kolder, Secretary Indra and other figures like Bilak, and Mestek were in favour of state occupation.⁶⁵

⁵⁷ Ibid.

⁵⁸ Ibid, 69.

⁵⁹ Jiri Valenta, "Revolutionary Change, Soviet Intervention, and "Normalization" in East-Central Europe," 131.

⁶⁰ Jiri Valenta, "The Bureaucratic Politics Paradigm and the Soviet Invasion of Czechoslovakia," 63.

⁶¹ Bromke, "Czechoslovakia and the World," 582.

⁶² Jiri Valenta, "The Bureaucratic Politics Paradigm and the Soviet Invasion of Czechoslovakia," 63.

⁶³ Fred H. Eidlin, "Capitulation, Resistance and the Framework of Normali-Zation: the August 1968 Invasion of Czechoslovakia and the Czechoslovak Response," 320.

⁶⁴ Ibid, 325.

⁶⁵ Ibid.

Those anti-reformists provided ‘evidence’ to Soviet Politburo of the ‘counterrevolutionary’ aspects of Dubcek’s reform to instigate Soviets to act.⁶⁶

d) Other factors

The existing international situation at the time of Prague Spring was favourable for Soviets to escape serious response from the great powers who were preoccupied in different parts of the World. For instance, China was shocked by internal protests in the wake of the Cultural Revolution. Students’ revolt in France in the spring of 1968 led to a domestic crisis in the state. The US, in turn, was busy with the war in Vietnam and could not generate viable policy towards Eastern Europe.⁶⁷ Moreover, Soviets believed that the American government would leave Czechoslovakia without any direct assistance because they looked for US-Soviet cooperation in the Vietnamese conflict and wanted the progress on talks on the arms race.⁶⁸ Hence, both sides accepted each other’s sphere of influence and were less likely to intervene in each other’s ‘internal affairs’.⁶⁹

2. What did Soviets achieve by invading Czechoslovakia? What did it lose?

a) Czechoslovakia’s pre and post invasion affairs

Although the program of democratization was issued by the local Communist Party, the developments in Czechoslovakia before the Soviet invasion of 1968 were incompatible with the USSR’s form of Communism. Czechoslovak reforms included changes in economic systems with the introduction of minor market forces, freedom of speech, freedom of the press, more human rights, no restrictions on political associations.⁷⁰ However, all the mentioned were perceived by Soviets as ideological innovations.⁷¹ Truth was that Dubcek attempted to re-popularize the local Communist Party by rejecting its most oppressive features.⁷²

⁶⁶ Jiri Valenta, “The Bureaucratic Politics Paradigm and the Soviet Invasion of Czechoslovakia,” 63.

⁶⁷ Bromke, “Czechoslovakia and the World,” 589.

⁶⁸ John C. Campbell. “Czechoslovakia: American Choices, Past and Future,” 17.

⁶⁹ Ibid, 17.

⁷⁰ Jiri Valenta, “Revolutionary Change, Soviet Intervention, and “Normalization” in East-Central Europe,” 130.

⁷¹ Bromke, “Czechoslovakia and the World,” 581.

⁷² Anna J. Stoneman, “Socialism with a Human Face: the Leadership and Legacy of the Prague Spring,” 105.

After the invasion, however, Soviets held most of the political leaders in their positions, their political activities, according to the Moscow Protocol, were restricted though.⁷³ The Protocol committed local leaders not to initiate any discussions regarding Czechoslovakia in the United Nations Security Council (UNSC).⁷⁴ Democratization processes, including economic reforms, were fully curbed. Czechoslovakia remained to be closely linked to Warsaw Pact.⁷⁵ Moreover, press censorship was re-imposed, political groups of non-communist nature were silenced again, while the influence of the Communist Party was re-ensured in all socio-political and economic levels.⁷⁶ As a result, Husak, who replaced the Dubcek in April 1969, brought Czechoslovakia back to the folds of political and economic orthodoxy.⁷⁷

According to Brown, local intellectuals formed the movement that no longer focused on democratization reforms but sought to overthrow the government entirely.⁷⁸ On January 6, 1969, Jan Palach, a student, set himself on fire in a central area of Prague as a protest against the free speech censorship.⁷⁹ As a result, the group formed of dissident intellectuals blamed Soviets for Palach's death, Czechoslovak government for betrayal, and local population for its inability to bring regime change.⁸⁰

b) Invasion consequences: Soviet-Europe relations

The Soviets tried to minimize the damage caused to its prestige and policies around the world as a result of an invasion of Czechoslovakia in 1938. They immediately started to justify the use of power by alleged counter-charges of Western subversion in the region.⁸¹ At the same time, Soviets claimed that the invasion was aimed to restore internal disorder among Communist camp, rather than to disturb the balance of power in Europe. Russian propaganda failed.⁸²

⁷³ Bromke, "Czechoslovakia and the World," 584.

⁷⁴ Fred H. Eidlin, "Capitulation, Resistance and the Framework of Normalization: the August 1968 Invasion of Czechoslovakia and the Czechoslovak Response," 329.

⁷⁵ Ibid, 329.

⁷⁶ Bromke, "Czechoslovakia and the World," 585.

⁷⁷ Adam Roberts, "Socialist Conservatism in Czechoslovakia". *The world Today* 26, (1970): 478.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/40394331>.

⁷⁸ Anna J. Stoneman, "Socialism with a Human Face: the Leadership and Legacy of the Prague Spring," 107.

⁷⁹ Ibid, 107.

⁸⁰ Ibid.

⁸¹ Bromke, "Czechoslovakia and the World," 585.

⁸² Ibid, 585.

Soviets won back the control on Czechoslovakia under the Warsaw Pact, meanwhile, the traditional sympathy of the local population was lost.⁸³ Czechoslovaks were disillusioned with Communist ideals that mobilized the masses before the invasion.⁸⁴

Soviets missed the opportunity to prove that they shifted from Stalinism to moderation of East-West détente. By using force in Czechoslovakia, Soviets shocked the international community, and the course of their foreign policy has been questioned.⁸⁵ Such a situation has created a widespread feeling of insecurity especially in communist states of Romania and Yugoslavia and alienated them. In the eyes of leadership in Bucharest and Belgrade Russians might use communist cause as a pretext to use force.⁸⁶ Thus, Romania, which is geographically close to the USSR, demanded the withdrawal of Warsaw Pact troops from Czechoslovakia.⁸⁷ The leadership at Bucharest also supported Czechoslovakia's right to independence.⁸⁸

Communist Party representatives from Western countries also joined the Romanian and Yugoslav protesters against the Soviet harsh policies in Czechoslovakia. Particularly, the Italian and French Parties, once pro-Moscow, now condemned the Soviet leadership and tried to cut themselves off from Soviet actions in Prague.⁸⁹ The British, Belgian, Dutch, Swiss, Austrian and Scandinavian parties followed the Soviet condemnation. Pro-Soviet parties from other parts of the world, particularly Japan, India, and Ceylon, took a similar stand.⁹⁰ At the same time, turmoil in the international communist movement played into the hands of China, one of the major adversaries of the USSR at the time who aimed to challenge the soviet version of Communism.⁹¹

Western Europe saw Soviet aggression as a revival of the Cold War. West Germany, particularly, was concerned about Kremlin's intentions mainly because Soviets' might have accused the Bonn of subversion in Eastern Europe. Kremlin also claimed to intervene in West Germany in case of

⁸³Adam Bromke, "Aftermath of Czechoslovakia," *Canadian Slavonic Papers* 11, (1969): 23.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/40866201>.

⁸⁴ Anna J. Stoneman, "Socialism with a Human Face: the Leadership and Legacy of the Prague Spring," 108.

⁸⁵ Ibid, 108.

⁸⁶ Bromke, "Czechoslovakia and the World," 586.

⁸⁷ Adam Bromke, "Aftermath of Czechoslovakia," 23. Bromke, "Czechoslovakia and the World," 586.

⁸⁸ Bromke, "Czechoslovakia and the World," 586.

⁸⁹ Ibid, 586.

⁹⁰ Bromke, "Czechoslovakia and the World," 586.

⁹¹ Adam Bromke, "Aftermath of Czechoslovakia," 23.

revival of Nazism. In response, however, NATO was ready to take actions and back the West Germans.⁹²

Moscow could not save its prestige among developing countries either. Many African, Asian, and Latin American USSR friendly nations strongly denounced the Soviet's brutal approach in Czechoslovakia. USSR was portrayed as a just another imperialist power ready to go beyond the one's sovereignty to reach own aims.⁹³

c) Invasion consequences: Soviet-US relations

The Czechoslovakia crisis occurred at a critical stage of US-USSR relations. At the time, American President Johnson and Russian Premier Kosygin were looking for a ground to negotiate on halting the arms race.⁹⁴ Thus, the US leadership tried to avoid deteriorations of its relations with Soviets over Czechoslovakia due to the importance of coming negotiations. However, Washington representatives were ready to reject any cultural exchanges with Warsaw Pact members as a boycott against Soviets' harsh policies in Czechoslovakia.⁹⁵ As a result, under the harsh critique at home, coming American-Soviet meetings were cancelled. Washington issued reinvigoration of NATO to ensure the security of Western Europe, while the gradual withdrawal of American troops from Western Germany was halted.⁹⁶ Moreover, a nuclear non-proliferation strategy was greatly opposed in US Senate, the significance of American nuclear superiority was emphasized, an extension of military aid to Israel as well as the continuation of Vietnam War was supported.⁹⁷ At the same time, US leadership realized that their direct response to Soviets in Prague would only have served as a pretext for Soviets to invade Czechoslovakia.⁹⁸

Conclusion

The decision-making made by Soviets was the result of an absence of unified common view at the Kremlin on the political struggle in Czechoslovakia. The fact that there were two camps, supporters and opponents of a military approach, made the final decision long and unexpected. It

⁹² Bromke, "Czechoslovakia and the World," 587.

⁹³ Ibid, 586.

⁹⁴ Ibid, 587.

⁹⁵ Ibid, 588.

⁹⁶ Ibid.

⁹⁷ Ibid.

⁹⁸ Ibid, 590.

is significant to emphasize the Soviets' attempts to negotiate with Dubcek's government on reforms and to avoid the invasion till the last moment. However, Dubcek's refusal to cooperate and varying complaints expressed from other leaders of Soviet satellite states in East Europe influenced the USSR government heavily.

The argument that Dubcek's reforms did not aim to threaten the Communist regime in the state is valid. However, Soviets could not risk the unity of Warsaw Pact because in case of failure the power and prestige of Czechoslovak Communist Party would collapse and will weaken the Soviet influence, while in case of Dubcek's triumph, other Warsaw Pact members possibly would wish to follow the line and issue democratization in their countries that would lead, in turn, to the disintegration of Warsaw Pact and Soviet regime in their states. Moreover, distorted information provided by leaders of Warsaw Pact members and KGB might generated the exaggerated threat of Dubcek's reforms and significantly affected the decision in favor of the invasion. Thus, for Soviets it was important to secure the power of local Communist Parties and to preserve the single form of ideology - Moscow led communism - to ensure the unity of Warsaw Pact, to oppose the NATO, and to undermine Chinese version of Communism. Hence, from the perspective of leadership at Kremlin, the invasion was inevitable.

The international situation in the world ensured USSR leaders that no direct response would proceed if they invade Prague. However, Soviets miscalculated the loss of prestige around the World. The portrayal of USSR as another imperial power in the third world would damage Soviets capability to discredit Western states for being colonial or imperial powers thus, to look for allies in the developing world. Similarly, pillars of Communist ideology started to be questioned by populations of pro-soviet Eastern European states. This led to the gradual degradation of communist regimes among Iron Curtain because people were disillusioned. Soviets' "triumph" in ensuring the unity of Warsaw Pact and revival of the power of the Czechoslovak Communist Party constructed fake representation of the Soviet bloc. However, the Prague Spring triggered the democratization process which, in turn, partially and gradually influenced the eventual collapse of the Iron Curtain and shortly after the Soviet Union. Moreover, the crisis led to the re-emergence of high hostility between Cold War adversaries allowing US and NATO to solidify its presence in Europe. Hence, Soviets lost more than they won in Czechoslovak crisis.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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